

IoT Based Automatic Door Unlocking System Using ESP32 Cam

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Abstract- The lightning-fast pace of technological innovation in today's society has raised important concerns with respect to the protection of personal information and privacy. Because of the rapid advancement of technology and the progression of industrialization, it is now absolutely necessary for every single person to protect their privacy and security. When it comes to recognizing authorized persons and reducing instances of fraudulent activities, robberies, and other types of social crimes, authentication is an extremely important consideration. Traditional methods of locking doors often include flaws that may be exploited by someone who are not authorized to access the building. In spite of the fact that there are alternatives available, such as video streaming and smart doorbells, these solutions have several drawbacks, including high prices, complexity, and security flaws. A Smart Door Unlock System that makes use of facial recognition technology is what we suggest as a solution to handle these issues and to increase the level of security. One of the components of our proposed system is an esp32-cam camera sensor, which allows for the capture and storage of photographs of persons. The device uses artificial intelligence to identify a person's face while they are standing in front of the door. After the picture has been acquired, it is compared with permitted faces that are recorded on the SD card that is included inside the esp32-cam. The door is unlocked by a solenoid lock if the person who is attempting to enter is permitted. In the event that the individual is not permitted to enter, the door will continue to be locked. Not only does this cutting-edge device not only take the role of conventional mechanical locks, but it also offers an increased level of safety. In addition to this, it provides a convenient solution for persons who may misplace their keys and makes it simpler for people with disabilities to get entry.

Index Terms- Authentication, esp32-cam, solenoid lock, security, facial recognition, artificial intelligence (AI).

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of security cannot be overstated in day-to-day living. In order for people to have access to certain approved information, authorization is of great assistance. Not only does security contribute to the maintenance of secrecy, but it also contributes to the maintenance of human life. A significant number of illegal acts are carried out in the society as a result of a lack of security; this throws light on the security issue, allowing it to be considered a noteworthy problem. Since this is the case, there is a need to increase the degree of security in order to preserve integrity [1]. A variety of methods, including fingerprints, facial recognition, passwords, pin configurations, and so on, may be used to accomplish authorization. Intruders may have a difficult time gaining access to these fingerprints and face recognition systems since they are so difficult to use. There are a variety of approaches that have been adopted for automatically accessing the doors, which contributes to the maintenance of security. However, some of the recommended solutions, such as gaining access to doors via the use of doorbells, were not successful in maintaining high levels of security. The construction of some systems that are done with the assistance of Raspberry Pi may be quite a costly and complicated endeavor [2]. The procedures that have been described above are not simple to maintain and may use a significant amount of electrical energy. Additionally, the gadgets are prone to being worn out. Using face recognition, the suggested approach helps to avoid the constraints that are associated with the technologies that are currently in use.

For the purpose of continually monitoring a person's face, the approach that has been developed includes a camera sensor with the model number esp32. It is possible to keep the faces of authorized individuals on the SD card that is included with the esp32 cam [3, 4]. When someone approaches the door, the esp32 cam is able to identify their face by comparing it to the permitted faces of authorized individuals stored in the database. This occurs whenever the person stands in front of the door. The algorithm known as "AI-Thinker" is used in the process of identifying and recognizing the face of a person. In the event that the individual is an authorized person, the door will be unlocked automatically [5]. Automatic locking of the door occurs in the event that the individual in question is not permitted to be there. The solution that is being suggested is both inexpensive and simple to keep up with. People who are impaired may find it easier to reach the doors with the assistance of this. The technology that is being developed has the capability of preventing trespassers from accessing the residence. It contributes to the provision of security to ordinary people at a price of reasonable affordability.

It has the potential to address the primary drawback of conventional lock systems, which are limited in the number of keys they can operate with.

The system that is being offered is comprised of Arduino idle software for the purpose of developing the code. Among the hardware components that make up this device are a relay module and an ftdi board. It has the potential to assist in the elimination of social crimes and stealing events.

The remainder of the article is devoted to discussing the associated work, the technique that was presented, the findings and analysis, the conclusion, and the references.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

W The smart anti-theft locking system that was proposed by Jahnavi S. and her colleagues [1] is trained with the characteristics of the authorized individuals and is saved in the database containing the information. The method starts with capturing the picture of a person using a raspberry pi camera. The Viola-Jones method is then used to do face detection when this step has been completed. With this approach, the detection of the item is carried out with a higher degree of precision. The Local Binary Pattern (LBP) method is used in order to accomplish the purpose of feature extraction and face detection. Through the creation of an intermediate picture, this method brings out the face traits that were present in the first illustration. In order to extract the local characteristics of the intermediate picture, the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) technique is used. A comparison is made between each face picture in the test set and the photos that were used in the training set. Whenever there is a match, the access is granted to the individual who is permitted to have it. If this is not the case, entrance to the door will be refused, and an alarm will be triggered to notify the individual. This study has a number of flaws, the most significant of which is that the method that is used to identify face points trains the model quite slowly.

The Lamia, Farhat [2] Barsha et al. provide a suggestion for an Automated Door Accessing System that would be designed for those who are visually impaired. This system will be affixed to the door in order to identify visits by facial recognition and advise users as to whether the guest is known or unknown. Additionally, users will be able to automatically unlock the door through voice command by utilizing a desktop program. In addition to being able to recognize any behavior that is considered to be extremely suspicious, such as a someone loitering in front of the door for a lengthy period of time, this device is also capable of producing an alarm in the form of an auditory signal in any circumstance. In order to determine whether or not the individual shown in the photograph is in possession of a potentially lethal weapon, the detection will be carried out on the image that was recorded. It is possible that a message will be sent to the user's family automatically in the event that an intruder attempts to break in. For the purpose of determining whether or not a person is there, sonar is installed outside the entrance. The Raspberry Pi camera is equipped with a Speaker that is attached to a USB port. This Speaker is responsible for providing voice alerts. In order to identify the face, a webcam is used. To identify potentially hazardous metal instruments, the system makes use of a detector circuit that was constructed using Arduino. There are two primary problems associated with this system: i) It does not reveal the face of the unauthorized individual, and ii) It is difficult to construct and keep up with.

The remotely accessible smart door lock [5] that was suggested by Adarsh V Patil and his colleagues may be entirely monitored and operated from a distant place by utilizing an android application on a smart phone. In this scenario, a Raspberry Pi equipped with a high-definition camera is activated when a visitor pushes a calling bell or push button at the entrance. The Raspberry Pi then sends a message to the owner, notifying them of the visitor's presence and streaming the visitor's live identification on the owner's mobile device via the internet. The owner may simply open/close the door remotely by inputting a password that was pre-set. Additionally, he is able to send an audio message to the guest by typing the correct text into the application that is installed on his smart phone. Switch, Video Camera, Raspberry Pi 3, Servo Motor, Raspbian Operating System, Motion Package, and Blynk Software are the components that are included in this system assemblage. This project provides the owner with the ability to remotely monitor his property and have access to it in real time. Additionally, it provides a means for the owner to leave his replies with the guest. The two most significant restrictions of this work are as follows: i) This project is only compatible with mobile devices, and ii) It is rather pricey.

The work that was offered by Manasi Jeste and colleagues [7] makes use of fingerprint reading and facial recognition as a kind of two-point authentication. Face recognition is the first authentication pin, while fingerprints are the second authentication pin. Face recognition is used to verify authentication. By using a hardware lock, the solution that has been described may be put into action. The software component is responsible for the training of facial recognition and fingerprint algorithms via the use of machine learning methods. The Local Binary Patterns Histograms (LBPH) method is used for the purpose of face recognition via its implementation. The face traits are brought to the forefront by this algorithm, which provides a more accurate description of the original picture. It is a mobile phone application that is used to construct the fingerprint recognition system. The application makes use of a fingerprint database that is stored on the user's mobile device, either pre-existing on the mobile device or capable of generating its own database.

Through the use of the Android app, the door may be opened if the individual's fingerprints and face are correctly identified as belonging to the same person. This effort has a number of restrictions, the most significant of which are as

follows: i) This project's complexity in terms of preserving security ii) It is more costly than other options because it requires a greater number of electrical components. The concept of a Wearable Device Used for Smart Doorbell in Home Automation System [8] was conceived by Abdul Basit and his colleagues. These devices are used for opening doors via the use of biometric authentication. Additionally, it presents the concept of storing the biometric information of visitors in a local database and recognizing them at a later time. When a visitor approaches and rings the bell, it records all of the essential information, including the visitor's voice, face image, and iris image, among other bits of information. This system maintains a record of each and every individual that comes to the residence. Moreover, it notifies the homeowner of any motion that occurs outside the house and makes it possible to communicate with the guest from any location. For the purpose of monitoring and managing the gadget, it is possible to control it using Smart Ring, which is completely necessary. i) The construction of this system is difficult, and ii) It is also costly.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of the project is to get entry to the door without the involvement of a human being. The esp32 cam is a tool that may be used to do this [6]. The system that is being suggested makes use of face detection and recognition in order to provide access to those who are permitted to participate. It is possible to do this by gathering and storing the photographs of the approved individuals in the database. The web server may then provide the esp32 cam with access to the photographs that have been saved in the database of the allowed individuals.

When a person approaches the door, the ESP32 CAM takes a photo of that person and then compares it to the images that are saved on the micro-SD card of the ESP32 CAM. This allows the ESP32 CAM to determine whether or not the person has access to the door. The micro-SD card is used to store the photographs that are taken by the ESP32 CAM, which is used to snap pictures of approved individuals. In order to facilitate the process of identifying the face of an authorized individual, the Smart ESP32 CAM-AI thinker is used. In the event that the individual is identified as permitted, the door will be opened; but, if they are not, the door will continue to be locked. The use of a solenoid lock as a hardware lock is one method for doing this [7,8]. The jumper wires are used to link all of the hardware components that are being used. It is possible to link the software components with the hardware components with the assistance of an FTDI board. The software that is necessary to develop components for face detection and identification for Arduino idle is called Arduino idle. electricity that is in excess and contributes to the powering of the whole circuit when it is necessary.

Figure 1. Proposed Architecture

For the purpose of resolving real-time issues and crimes such as thefts, robberies, and looting private data, among other things, the suggested model architecture, which is shown in Figure 1. In addition, the model that has been developed is helpful for elderly and handicapped individuals, who have a great deal of difficulty while attempting to access conventional lock systems. The project contributes to the achievement of secrecy, which is necessary for the authorities to accomplish while they are working on critical missions.

Fig 2. Transactions of the proposed system

A. Facial Recognition

This system enhances security by transitioning from traditional mechanical locks to advanced facial recognition methods. It also benefits individuals who may lose keys or require easier access, such as those with disabilities.

1. Face Detection Algorithm: -

- Step 1: Resize the input image to different scales, creating an image pyramid.
- Step 2: Utilize the P-Net (part of the ESP-WHO module) to obtain bounding box regression vectors. These vectors define the faces' positions.
- Step 3: Feed all images to the R-Network, which filters out false positives and provides facial landmark positions.

2. Face Recognition Algorithm: -

- Step 1: Capture input from the ESP32-CAM for facial detection.
- Step 2: Iterate through a group of authorized persons (stored data) to detect faces.
- Step 3: Recognize the face using landmarks and image resolution.
- Step 4: Identify authorized and unauthorized individuals by drawing bounding boxes around their faces.
- Step 5: Confirm authorized persons based on key facial points.

B. Authentication System

Authentication System with ESP32-CAM This module focuses on authentication, a critical factor in determining a person's identity. Leveraging the ESP32-CAM, we achieve reliable identification at the door. Here's how it works:

1. Authorized Person Recognition:

- Step 1: Store photos of authorized individuals on the WebSocket Server of the ESP32-CAM.
- Step 2: When a visitor appears at the door, capture their photo using the camera.
- Step 3: Loop through the stored authorized images.
- Step 4: If the visitor's face matches any of the authorized images: Unlock the door. Set the active relay to true (indicating authorization).

Step 5: If the visitor's face doesn't match any authorized images: Lock the door. Set the active relay to false. This system seamlessly transitions between authorized and unauthorized access, enhancing security while ensuring ease of use.

C. Extension and Verification

This system provides a seamless transition between authorized and unauthorized access, enhancing security while maintaining convenience. Unlike conventional locks, it operates independently without relying on external software applications

Testing the Proposed System: Access Authorization and Face Recognition:

1. Scenario: Authorized Person Grants Access:

- Step 1: An authorized person decides to grant access to other individuals.
- Step 2: Pictures of these other persons are captured using the ESP32-CAM.
- Step 3: The captured images are sent to WebSocket Server.
- Step 4: When any of these individuals appear in front of the door later:
 - Their face is recognized.
 - If recognized as authorized, the door unlocks using a solenoid lock.

2. Scenario: Unauthorized Access:

- Step 1: If an unauthorized person (who still needs limited access) approaches the door:
 - Their picture is taken.
- Step 2: The picture is stored on the WebSocket Server.
- Step 3: When this person appears again:
 - Their face is detected and compared.
 - If recognized as authorized, the door unlocks.
 - Otherwise, the door remains locked and the buzzer turns On

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In the proposed system, facial point detection is accomplished via the use of the ESP32 CAM, which captures and compares pictures that are stored in the memory of the device. Through the use of the Arduino IDE, the ESP32 CAM is able to produce an IP address that is associated with a web page that allows for face enrollment. Specifically, the system is able to detect real-time face photographs, which significantly improves security. There is a solenoid lock that is integrated into the system for the purpose of electrically locking and unlocking doors. The latch action is handled by an electromagnetic mechanism. When compared to traditional locks that use Bluetooth, the solenoid lock has a reaction time that is much quicker, with a latency of less than two seconds. This is in contrast to Bluetooth systems, which have response times that are more than four seconds and a latency of three seconds. Through the use of Wi-Fi for code upload and face registration, the suggested system is able to circumvent the complications that are characteristic of Bluetooth connections. It places an emphasis on cost-effectiveness and low power consumption, attributing these benefits to the solenoid lock, which functions independently of software requirements. The power usage of the system is between 5 and 6 watts, but the power consumption of traditional locks is often more than 6 watts to begin with. When compared to systems that are linked by Bluetooth, the reaction time and delay time are greatly reduced. This substantiates the practical benefits that the system possesses in contrast to alternatives that are based on Bluetooth. A number of aspects, including reaction time, delay time, power consumption, and simplicity of setup, were taken into consideration throughout the investigation.

The hardware implementation is visually represented in the figure 3 below, providing a comprehensive overview of the system. The illustration includes key components such as user addition, access control, home screen interface, authorized user status, unauthorized user status, and door locked status. This graphical representation serves as a quick reference for understanding the various stages and functionalities embedded in the hardware setup. Each element depicted in the figure contributes to the seamless operation of the system, illustrating the process from user addition to access control, and ultimately determining whether the door is in an authorized, unauthorized, or locked state. This visual guide enhances the clarity of the hardware structure, aiding in a better understanding of the system's workflow.

Fig 3. (a)Home Screen (b)Adding User (c)Access Control (d)Authorized (e)Door Unlocked (f)Unauthorized

a) Comparison with related works:

Based on the information shown in Table 1, the proposed system surpasses the applications that are already in use by providing a variety of features that emphasize its strengths. The drawbacks that are seen in traditional lock systems are addressed by this product, which excels in delivering a wide range of features at a price point that is both cost-effective and compact within its dimensions.

b) Applications:

The locking and unlocking of doors is the core purpose of this project; nevertheless, its usefulness extends to a variety of areas, including fingerprint identification, security pins, and other gesture recognitions. The system is appropriate for real-time applications, such as intelligent attendance systems, safeguarding areas like banks and sensitive office rooms, and other similar applications. The low cost of this solution makes it more accessible, which in turn makes it a cost-effective solution for a broad variety of problem situations.

c) Attacks and Threats

The vulnerabilities that exist in the design and development of Internet of Things apps make it feasible for a variety of sorts of attacks to be launched against such applications. These days, there has been an upsurge in the number of cyber assaults against Internet of Things devices. Taking into consideration the findings of the literature review, we have implemented the required precautions in order to protect the proposed system from a number of potential assaults that may be mounted against it. A few types of assaults include cyber-attacks, system attacks, and authorized attacks.

- Authorized Attack:**

An unauthorized person is responsible for this attack since they gained access to the system and caused it to malfunction. There is a suggested mechanism that prevents the lock from opening in the event that an unauthorized individual attempts to enter the door. Due to the fact that the face is not recognized, the camera will continue to refuse to open even if an intruder manages to smash it and attempt to enter the property.

- System attack:**

Attacks on the system is another kind of hazard that the program faces. inside the framework of this suggested system, all of the data and face pictures of the users are only saved inside the system via a specific Internet Protocol (IP) address. The IP address is concealed, and the only person who can access it is the owner or author of the asset. Only via the use of the internet, which is connected with a particular URL, is it possible to manipulate data and make any changes to the data.

- cyber-attack:**

Most cyber assaults are carried out via the use of the internet. Intruders are able to get access to the programs and take control of them using this method. It is not possible to get access to the suggested system over the internet. In contrast to large systems, which need a link to the internet, it is not feasible to cause the system to malfunction. This is something that may be accomplished via the personal internal connection of our system to the gadgets that are available to users.

Methods Features	NgoTun g Son [9]	Kenici Yoned a [11]	Ivo Slugan ovic [12]	Gurlove Singh [14]	Zhaon anMu [15]	Proposed System
Wi-Fi	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Bluetooth	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Ease of Setup	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Low
Camera Support	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Power Consumption	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium	Low
Authentication	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Web Application	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes
Automatic Unlock	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes

Table 1. Comparison with the Existing Systems

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CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the approach that has been described offers a huge step forward in terms of offering security solutions that are both user-friendly and not prohibitively expensive. The integration of hardware components that are simple to maintain, such as the solenoid lock, relay module, FTDI board, jumper wires, and ESP32 CAM, guarantees that the product is both practical and convenient. This is accomplished by putting an emphasis on simplicity and readily accessible components. Not only does the face recognition function for unlocking doors accommodate to the requirements of those who are old or handicapped, but it also helps to reduce the number of mistakes that occur during the recognition process. The capabilities of the system to perform continuous monitoring via the use of the ESP CAM improve security measures by preventing unwanted access and guaranteeing a watchful surveillance that is present around the clock. It is also important to note that the flexibility of the system across a variety of industries, such as banks, businesses, and server rooms, highlights its versatility and potential for protecting sensitive information. The solution that has been presented is in line with the current trend of automation, which promotes efficiency and dependability. This is accomplished by decreasing the amount of human interaction. The implementation of power management via the relay module is evidence of a dedication to environmentally responsible practices within the organization. Furthermore, the system's accessibility and scalability, in addition to the opportunity for simple updates, position it as a resilient solution that can be adapted to meet the ever-changing requirements of the organization. In addition, the system that is being presented solves practical problems by providing a solution for misplaced keys, therefore reducing the discomfort that is associated with key memorizing. In general, the system that has been offered not only satisfies the existing requirements for security, but it also sets the groundwork for future improvements and developments in the field of automated access control systems.

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